

QUALITY PRACTICES IN INDUSTRIES: INTEGRATING ISO9000, TQM AND QUALITY AWARDS

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Abstract

In the atmosphere of cut- throat business competition, industries are compelled to adopt quality culture in their organization. There were many studies carried in past to examine the critical factors of quality practices mostly based on several frame work suggested by researchers & different business excellence models such as MBNQA,EFQM,AFQM etc. Quality Management System (QMS) deals with the entire organization and it has many challenges to the managers to fulfill quality requirements starting from product design to customer satisfaction. As ISO 9000, TQM and Quality awards are most popular and extensively used globally; present paper provides the integrating approach for ISO 9000, TQM and quality awards in context to Indian Industries

Keywords: Quality Management System (QMS), ISO 9000, TQM, Quality Awards, Quality practices

Abbreviations: ISO: International organization for standardization, MBNQA: Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award, EFQM: European Foundation for Quality Management, AFQM: Australian Foundation for Quality Management RGNQA: Rajiv Gandhi National Quality Award

1. INTRODUCTION

Opportunities for global-minded manufacturers are abundant, not only in servicing the needs of the market but in creating products adhering to new business models that ultimately will ensure future global markets. Never in the past has the role of the quality managers has been as crucial and exciting as now. The on- going economic reforms programs has created for them infinite opportunities for improving quality at international level so that every company can dent into the international market and make its own place in terms of increased market share.

2. QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Quality Management System (QMS) is a management function in totality which deals with ensuring quality level of out coming product to achieve customer satisfaction. Quality Management System (QMS) includes entire organization and it has many challenges to the managers to fulfill quality requirements with an ultimate objective to achieve positive performance outcomes. The aims of the businesses may differ, but the importance of customers is a matter of common interest and the ability of organizations to adapt to new customer requirements on a global market is of vital importance for long-term success. Quality management has been recognized as a major edge for competitiveness and long-term profitability. Typical QMS focus on strategic planning, customer satisfaction, analysis of information, team work and training and effective leadership. In nut shell QMS system should meet all the requirements of achieving total quality. Organizations all over the world are using different techniques for quality improvement. ISO 9000 is both a management tool, and a source of competitive advantage, with the potential to stimulate the company in moving towards Total Quality Management (TQM). After more than two decades since quality became part of managers' everyday lexicon, total quality management (TQM) and ISO 9000 have taken the centre stage.

3. ISO 9000, TQM & QUALITY AWARDS:

ISO 9000 consists of a set of international standards for running a business in an effective manner. *ISO 9000 standards* of Quality Management were introduced in 1987 by International organization for standardization (ISO), a world wide federation of national standards bodies in 1947 to promote the development of standardization and facilitate the International exchange of goods & services. There after ISO 9000 family underwent three revisions, first one in 1994, second in 2000 and the latest one in 2008. New *ISO 9001:2008* families of standards were published in November 2008. It focuses on how the provisions of this standard can be applied for continual improvement of quality and how it helps in international accreditation of an organization and its program. The essence of ISO 9000 is for a company to "document what it does and do what it documents." When properly facilitated and used, the documentation developed in the facilitation process and the ISO 9000 registration and audit process itself becomes a management tool to promote excellence throughout the business. An essential feature of ISO 9000 is that it does not prescribe quality standards. The registered companies are free to define the quality standards or "best practices" that are sufficient to meet the needs of their customers and market within which they operate.

All that ISO 9000 requires is that the applicable standards are documented in a certain way.

Total Quality Management (TQM) is a philosophical approach adopted for designing structured system to manage the quality of products, processes, and resources of organization in order to satisfy its internal and external customers, as well as its suppliers. Its main objective is to provide customer satisfaction through continuous improvement. International quality accreditation is always a selling argument. The quality award is a natural development from quality certification programs. Since quality certification is an important need felt by suppliers and buyers ,worldwide acceptability of local certification is necessary by various counts and at present there are about five-dozen independent certification bodies acting globally including private and governmental agencies .

Firms that seek to distinguish themselves are seeking the next motivational level for quality excellence. Most awards have derived their guideline from the MBNQA-Malcolm Baldrige

National Quality Award and the EFQM - European Foundation Quality Model, Deming prize etc.

4. REVIEW ON QUALITY PRACTICES

At first glance, one would think that TQM and ISO 9000 do not have much in common, other than the fact that they both deal with the topic of quality. One is a philosophy of what makes up a quality organization, and the other is a set of rules that a quality organization might undertake. Quality Awards are other important aspects in modern era for evaluating growth, quality practices and work culture in any organization.

ISO 9000 benefits are mentioned in past, Durant [1] and Rabbit [2] recommended ISO certification for continuous improvement opportunities to build quality image of firm. Kochan [3] Focused on Broader sense of ISO 9000 adoption for obtaining Global Standardization. Gustav [4] appreciated ISO 9000 standards for developing effective work culture in industries. However, Withers [5] and Brown [6] shown disappointments with the outcomes of ISO 9000.

Total Quality Management (TQM) concept primarily based on philosophical approach, is another popular practice appraised by several scholars. Similar to ISO 9000 there were several studies carried in past to measure the outcomes of TQM as well, several definitions were suggested by global Quality who contributed their own Quality philosophies in TQM are Edward Deming, Joseph Juran, Philip B. Crosby, Armand V. Feigenbaum and Ishikawa. Studies have examined ISO900-TQM linkages in past. Moreno-Luzon [7] found most small enterprises are forced by customers to adopt ISO 9000 certification. Askey [8] defined the path from ISO 9000 registration to TQM. Bettos David [9] mentioned that ISO 9000 is beginning of TQM process. Shams-ur Raheman [10] argued that ISO 9000 as managerial approach while TQM is an organizational approach. Rao [11] highlighted about significant difference between ISO 9000, TQM practices and organizational performance.

Deming prize was instituted in 1951, the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) was established in 1987 and the European Quality Award (EQA) was introduced in 1991. Panton [12] was pioneer in advocating Business Excellence Model into quality race

while Finlay[13] made the initial comparison among ISO 9000, Deming based TQM and Malcolm Baldrige Model.

5. FRAMEWORK FOR QUALITY PRACTICES:

Quality Gurus such as Deming, Crosby and Juran did not actually developed any implementation frameworks; they documented some guidelines to follow. Saraph [14] suggested the initial instrument for measuring the quality practices later Flynn [15], Ahire [16] and Samson [17] developed the frame work for quality management research

The most popular constructs, as per there order of appearance are:

5.1 Top Management Support

Senior leaders of an organization need to set directions to create customer orientation, clear and visible quality values and expectations of stack holders.

5.2 Customer Focus

Organizations depend on their customers as quality begins with customers and also ends with them. Customer- focused organizations produce as per the need of customers finally wants to provide them satisfaction.

5.3 Process Management

The systematic identification and management of the various processes are means of identifying and managing opportunities for improvements. It is broadly based on the simple but famous Deming cycle of Plan-Do-Check-Act.

5.4 Employee Involvement

Every employee has internal customers and their requirement is first step towards TQM. The success story of any organization is dependent on level of effectiveness and extent of employee involvement.

5.5 Supplier Management

Supplier quality is an important dimension of quality management as defective incoming materials and parts lead to process and product quality problems. Maintaining good supplier relationship is acknowledged as a key factor in maintaining competitive advantage.

5.6 Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management enables employee to develop and utilize their full potential and efforts to build and maintain a work environment with employee support climate.

5.7 Information Analysis

Effective communication and information analysis provides assistance within the company and externally, as it covers entire product cycle of design, development, manufacturing.

5.8 Employee Training

Training employees in quality concepts increases the effectiveness of quality improvement activities which require employee involvement. In other words, training contributes to successful implementation of quality management systems in a firm.

5.9 Strategic planning

Strategies are important for successful outcomes. The effective planning of strategies is needed to be deployed effectively to achieve desired performance and to meet benchmarks.

Table 1 represents the important constructs of TQM

6. INTEGRATING ISO 9000, TQM AND QUALITY AWARDS

The role of a quality manager is one that is constantly evolving. With increased demands on manufacturing operations and efficient services, quality managers are finding themselves subject to strict guidelines from both their customers and regulatory bodies. Historically individual programs were developed at the plant level to address quality needs; however, quality managers are now taking an approach that includes a complete enterprise wide view of the business based on adoption of successful quality practices viz. ISO 9000, TQM and Quality awards although specified in different structures but has substantial linkages as shown in **Figure 1**. *Business Excellence Models* are another popular tool practiced by several organizations with an objective to win quality awards at global level such as MBNQA, EFQM, and AFQM .In India RGNQA is being recognized as most prestigious quality award in line with other global awards. **Table 3** represents the constructs of most popular global Business Excellence Models and RGNQA.

CONCLUSION

Unlike the experience in the broader quality management (QM) area, for ISO 9000, the relationships between management practices associated with the standard and performance is relatively under-researched. This has contributed to a general lack of clarity on how the standard works and how effective it is in generating the espoused benefits in current perspectives. TQM includes both an empirical component associated with statistics, and an explanatory component that is associated with management, of both people and processes. The terms "hard" and "soft" are commonly used to represent these two components. TQM brought recognition to the fact that tasks can be categorized as value adding or not. The obvious corollary is that non-value adding tasks would be eliminated and the value adding ones improved. Many process design and operation tools have been highlighted in TQM, such as statistical process control, Kanban and flexible organization, just to name the tip of the iceberg. This study included frame-work; individual findings and quality awards to examine important quality practice for integrating ISO 9000, TQM and quality awards. Present study is based on the findings of literature review of 52 studies carried in past, with an attentive focus on the suggestions of several scholars & their frame-work with an objective to integrate most popular quality management practices. ISO 9000, TQM and Quality awards although specified in different structure & philosophy, the review supports that each QMS is linked with other in attaining performance improvement of organization. The integration approach to ISO 9000, TQM and Quality award will be useful to various quality practitioners & other researchers to understand quality practices associated with organizational performance improvements.

Table 1: Important Constructs of TQM

Constructs	Recommended/Consented By:
Top Management support/Leadership	Saraph et al (1989), Flynn et al (1994), Dale BG (1995), Ahire et al (1996), Brown et al (1996), Samson et al (1999)
Strategic Planning	Dean, (1994); Quazi et al (1998), Anderson et al (1999); Rao et al (1999), Samson et al (1999)
Customer focus	Saraph et al (1989), Flynn et al (1994), Ahire et al (1996), Brown et al (1996), Samson et al (1999)
Information Analysis	Deming (1986), Saraph et al (1989), Ahire et al (1996), Brown & Weile (1996), Samson et al (1994)

Constructs	Recommended/Consented By:
Human Resource Management	Mohanty et al (1994), Ahire et al (1996), Samson & Terziovski (1999)
Process improvement/Management	Saraph et al (1989), Flynn et al (1994), Askey J.M et al (1994), Brown & Weile (1996), Black & Porter et al (1999); Samson & Terziovski (1999)
Supplier Management	Saraph et al (1989), Flynn et al (1994), Ahire et al (1996), Brown et al (1996), Samson et al (1999), Black & Porter et al (1999)
Employee Involvement/Empowerment/Training	Saraph et al (1989), Flynn et al (1994), Ahire et al (1996), Brown et al (1996), Anderson et al (1999)
Process/Product Design	Juran(1981), Deming(1986), Saraph(1989)
Corporate Culture	Askey(1994), Rao (1999) Anderson et al (1999)
Continuous/Continual improvement	Ahire(1996)

Figure 1: Integrating ISO 9000, TQM and Quality Awards

Table 2 : Constructs of popular Business Excellence Models

Popular Awards	Constructs	Total Constructs
MBNQA(USA) Malcolm Balridge National Quality Award	Leadership, Information analysis and knowledge management, Strategic planning, Customer focus, Work force management, Process management, Quality results	07

Popular Awards	Constructs	Total Constructs
EFQM(UK) European Foundation for Quality Management	Leadership, Information analysis , Strategic planning, Customer focus, Work force management, Process management, Resource management, Employee satisfaction, Quality results	09
AFQM(Australia) Australian Foundation for Quality Management	Leadership, Information analysis and knowledge management, Strategic planning, Customer focus, Work force management, Process management, Quality results	07
RGNQA(India) Rajiv Gandhi National Quality Award	Leadership, Strategic planning, Customer focus, Work force management, Process management, Resource management, Employee satisfaction, Impact on society, Quality results	09

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